

Lost in Training?

RDMTraining4NFDI - a base service for modular certified training

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Abstract

The past few years have seen a large number of initiatives and working groups that have developed collections of training materials for different target groups and with different thematic focuses, learning objectives and competence profiles in the field of Research Data Management (RDM). It is hard to keep track: Which materials and content are relevant for whom? How can generic content be adapted to subject-specific needs? Which training formats are suitable for which target group? And how can learning units be certified?

The base service *Research Data Management Training for NFDI* (RDMTraining4NFDI) [1] offers a modular collection of primarily existing fundamental RDM training materials, featuring documented and tested training formats and methods that take the Learning Objective Matrix [2] into account. Materials created in this project, such as best-practice guides, will be made freely available as Open Educational Resources (OER) under the CC-BY license and registered in DALIA [3] including metadata. By providing access to these materials, consortia can efficiently develop their own community-specific adaptations of the training and build capacity quickly.

In cooperation with four pilot consortia we collect existing (data type-specific) RDM teaching materials as well as learning objectives and how-to guidelines from the four NFDI consortia which form the foundation for a design document, with a future perspective of including materials of all consortia. In addition to the actual teaching materials, various training formats, didactic concepts, learning resources and competency levels are identified and/or supplemented. This approach helps facilitate data-type-specific adaptation of the learning objectives matrix, support trainers in structuring and prioritizing their teaching content, and incorporate methods of engagement. This centralized support in instructional design, didactics and organization structuring are partially based on the Instructor Training from The Carpentries [4] and the "Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management" [5] to ensure the use of evidence-based teaching methods.

To assess the relevance, clarity as well as practicality of the training content and delivery methods after domain-specific adaption, three pilot training formats will be carried out with data stewards and RDM professionals: a flexible online workshop series, an intensive onsite Summer School and prospectively in the integration phase, a 10-month-long course building upon

the experience gained from the RDM certificate course developed by TH Köln, ZB MED and fdm.nrw [6].

The results will serve as the basis for designing and creating data-type-specific training courses. Additionally, synergies with concepts (such as metadata schema for RDM [7] and Train-the-Trainer [8] of existing initiatives such as Dini/Nestor AG Forschungsdaten [9], Edu-Bricks [10]) and other basic services have been build and further to be explored to enhance (existing) training efforts across the NFDI landscape.

Besides strengthening cooperation and networking within the NFDI and externally, we address the strong demand from the NFDI consortia [11] for standardized and certified training within the NFDI by exploring options for certifying RDM training.

In our presentation, we will provide insights into the current collection and ongoing work, outline our process for identifying certification options, and offer an outlook on the integration phase.

Keywords: Research Data Management (RDM), Training, Certification

Resources

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Author contributions

Mareike Wohltmann: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Project administration

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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